

Effect of Micro, Small Business on economic Growth: A case Study of Konyokonyo Market, Custom Market and Jebel Market in Juba City South Sudan

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Abstract

This research article's goal is to analyze the impact of micro, small businesses on economic growth through a case study of Juba, South Sudan's Konyokonyo, Custom, and Jebel markets. It also looks at the difficulties faced by this sector in obtaining loans from most financial institutions as well as the significance that micro, tiny businesses play in creating jobs. The study gathered information from 51 respondents who were micro and small business owners in the konyokonyo market, custom market, and jebel market in Juba City. The information was analyzed using the SPSS statistical package with the help of statistical tools like tables, pie charts, bar graphs, histograms, frequencies, and percentages. According to the report, micro and small businesses have made a significant contribution to South Sudan's economic growth and development through the creation of jobs, GDP, the eradication of poverty, the empowerment of women, and the support of larger businesses. Nevertheless, despite the sector's significant contributions, South Sudan's micro and small businesses face a number of difficulties, including a lack of cash, a lack of knowledge, problems with energy and power, and faulty record-keeping. The study's findings support the idea that government at all levels and essential stakeholders should help micro and small businesses in order to ensure their long-term viability. The researcher suggests that there should be monitoring and supervision by the sectors that provide credit to micro small businesses to ensure that operators in the konyokonyo, custom, and jebel markets use the loans for the intended purposes in order to reduce default and collapse rates for long-term existence.

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Introduction

Academics and decision-makers alike have acknowledged the contribution that small and micro businesses contribute to innovation, the advancement of industrial growth, the creation of jobs, and market competitiveness (FBeck et al., 2005; Thurik and Wennekers, 2004; Ayagari et al., 2003; Davidson and Henderson, 2002; Storey, 1994). Small and micro businesses are extremely important to the economy of both industrialized and developing nations, according to their governments. As a result, the government frequently announces initiatives designed expressly to help the small company sector. For instance, the UK Government's small company development program has put a strong emphasis on expanding companies Audretsch and Thurik, (2004); Johnson et al (2000). Similar to this, Getz and Petersen (2005) claimed that the EU member nations' programs for supporting small businesses were designed to emphasize expansion and employment creation. The potential worth of micro and small firms has been recognized in the quickly emerging nations like South Korea and India. Particularly in South Sudan and East Africa, micro and small enterprises play significant and unprecedented roles in entrepreneurial development, job creation, and poverty alleviation. However, the majority of these micro-small firms only get sporadic and disorganized government support. Despite this, a tiny number of fiercely competitive micro and small enterprises are working hard to boost the economy, create jobs, and advance efforts to fight poverty. The creation of new jobs by micro-small firms has been highlighted as having the most potential. They can also distribute the advantages of industrial development more widely due to their geographic reach and their capacity for adapting to changing conditions. Creating jobs, utilizing local resources, reducing rural-urban migration, and distributing industrial enterprises more evenly across the nation were the main goals of the government's program for the development of small-scale industries, according to the researcher. However, on May 27, 2022, the World Bank supported women's empowerment by approving 70 million US dollars for the international development association (IDA) in order to promote gender equality. Micro-small firms make up the majority of enterprises in South Sudan. Approximately 70% of the South Sudanese work force can be employed in this area. They include everything from products used for subsistence farming to agribusinesses, light manufacturing, textile and apparel industries, restaurants, financial services, building trades, and others. The development of these micro and small enterprises has significantly suffered from a lack of attention and assistance, shifting the emphasis away from entrepreneurship and toward an increase in petty trade.

Statement of the Research Problem

In South Sudan and Sudan, small companies continue to be crucial to the provision of services. According to World Bank data from 2000, small firms in Sudan accounted for more than 70% of all industrial operations (World Bank, 2000). Major tools for reducing poverty and fostering economic growth are small companies. A significant source of local technology and talent development is micro, tiny businesses. Due to the labor-intensive nature of their activities, they also generate additional jobs. Despite all of these noteworthy accomplishments, this industry nevertheless receives a terrible amount of attention. Some of the causes may be attributed to their size, fragmented nature, lack of knowledge, poor level of education, inadequate training, and lack of entrepreneurial abilities, among other things. Despite this, certain emerging nations, like Taiwan, South Korea, India, and China, have taken advantage of the potential of this industry. What hinders South Sudan's development? Therefore, this research seeks to identify viable solutions to the problems this sector is facing so that its potential can be fully realized for South Sudan's economic development and prosperity.

Research Objectives

General Objective

This research's goal is to examine how small businesses and microbusinesses affect economic growth. It does this through a case study of Juba, South Sudan's Konyokonyo Market, Custom Market, and Jebel Market.

Specific Objectives are:

(i) To evaluate the varied activities of micro-small enterprises in South Sudan, (ii) investigate the issues that impede their expansion and survival, (iii) research the elements that promote their expansion and survival, and (iv) propose long-term solutions to assist the growth of small businesses. The purpose of the current study is to elucidate the research questions. (1) What obstacles prevent small enterprises from operating effectively and efficiently? What corrective actions may be taken (ii) to improve the growth and performance of small businesses? (iii) Are there developed sustainable methods to encourage the development of small businesses?

Research Design

A descriptive research survey was employed as the study design.

The research's aim to explain a particular feature of the business population by choosing a sample of micro-small business owners and asking them to fill out questionnaires made the design used for the study acceptable.

Significance of the Study

In addition to serving as a reference point for future research on related subjects, the study's findings will assist micro-small businesses in using its findings to enhance their operations and services. They will also aid practitioners and academics in understanding how these businesses develop and survive, as well as in determining whether their current management practices and policies are appropriate for emerging economies.

Scope of the Study

The Juba City Markets Area was primarily the focus of the research investigation.

The research mainly focuses on elements that limit the expansion and survival of micro-small businesses in the Juba city Area.

Study Limitation

The study's breadth was constrained by time, logistical, and financial constraints. Only a portion of the micro and small businesses located in Juba City's Konyokonyo Market, Custom Market, and Jebel Market were examined by the researcher. Despite the researcher's efforts and strategies to explain the possible advantages of the study, some respondents failed to complete the questionnaires that were supplied to them, which reduced the number of respondents who were engaged in the study.

Literature Review

This chapter discusses and expands on the theories that researchers and practitioners utilized to conduct this study, drawing from their scholarly writings, papers, and journal articles that explain the challenges that limit the efficient running, expansion, and survival of micro-small businesses in Juba City. There is no one, consistently acceptable definition of a small business, according to Kanburi's 2009 report on "assessing the performance of micro and small-scale organizations." Businesses vary in terms of their size, revenue, and workforce (Storey, 1994). Therefore, a definition that uses a measure of size (number of workers, turnover, profitability, worth, and others) might cause all enterprises to be categorized as tiny when used to one

sector, but the same size definition could have a different outcome when applied to a different sector (large businesses). When the Bolton Committee (1971) introduced a "economic" and a "statistical" definition, they were the first to attempt to resolve the defining dilemma. According to their economic definition, a company qualifies as tiny if it satisfies the following three criteria: If it is run personally and without the aid of a codified management structure by the owners or part owners, If their market share is only a small portion, If it is autonomous in the sense that it is not a part of a major corporation, The group also developed a definition of "statistical" to be applied in three key areas, In order to determine the size of the small business sector and its impact on employment, exports, foreign exchange, etc., evaluating how much the economic contribution of the small company sector has changed through time.

The researcher categorized the business sector into three components:

0 to 9 employee microbusinesses, 10 to 99 employee smallbusinesses, and 100 to 499 employee mediumbusinesses. According to Grindle et al. (1988), small enterprises are organizations with less than 25 regular employees and fixed assets (excluding land) valued up to \$50,000 USD. Small enterprises are defined as organizations with less than 50 workers and at least half of their production sold, according to Mead (1984) and the United States Agency for International Development (1990s).

United Nations International Development Organization (UNIDO) definition for Developing Countries:

Small businesses with less than five employees, medium-sized businesses with 20 to 99 employees, and large enterprises with more than 100 employees are all categories of company. Definition of Developed Countries by the United Nations International Development Organization (UNIDO): Small firms with fewer than 29 employees, medium-sized enterprises with 100 to 499 employees, and large organizations with more than 500 employees are all considered microbusinesses. We may infer from the different definitions given above that there isn't a distinct definition for small enterprises (micro-small businesses). Consequently, an operational definition is necessary.

Definitions of Small Businesses in South Sudan

Although there are several definitions of small enterprises, the most widely accepted criterion for small size firm has historically been the number of workers. The Statistical Service (SS) classifies firms as follows in its industrial statistics: smaller companies with fewer than ten workers and larger companies with ten or more employees. The amount of fixed assets and the number of workers inside the company are other criteria used to categorize small enterprises.

Microbusinesses are defined as those with up to 5 employees and fixed assets (including real estate) worth no more than \$100,000.

Small Business: Employ 6 to 29 people and have fixed assets worth at least \$100,000. Employ between 30 and 99 people and have fixed assets of up to \$1 million MSME Activities, Income Levels, and Poverty Reduction (Agyapong D., 2010).

Rationale for Micro Small Businesses

Micro-small enterprises repurpose money that would have otherwise been sitting idle. Small and micro enterprises make effective use of resources that may not be relevant to giant corporations in order to grow their operations and the overall national economy. Konyokonyo Market, Custom Market, and Jebel Market have all been recognized for their micro-small enterprises run by indigenous entrepreneurs. Entrepreneurship is said to thrive naturally in

the small business sector. It has the ability to offer the best environment for enabling business owners to best utilize their skills and achieve their professional objectives. Small companies are viewed as a crucial launching pad for development, job creation, and social advancement in all successful economies. Micro-small enterprises are labor intensive, employing more workers per unit of capital than large businesses. Micro-small enterprises are becoming a crucial component of employment-related initiatives in less developing countries as a result of the realization that they significantly contribute to job creation. A sizable share of the workforce is employed by small firms, which are also frequently the biggest employers in emerging nations. Additionally, they give people a useful platform to express their entrepreneurship and help spread economic activity across the nation (Nelson 1987). Micro-small businesses operating in Konyokonyo Market, Custom Market, and Jebel Market in Juba City also promote local technological know-how. Small businesses have proven their powerful propellant effect for rapid economic growth. This is due to their size, location, capital investment, and capacity to generate more employment. These small businesses contribute to the use of regional technology to produce goods that go above and beyond what the regional market requires. Local kente wavers are an example of a micro-small business that serves the needs of the underprivileged and operates at Konyokonyo Market, Custom Market, and Jebel Market in Juba City. These enterprises mostly employ local resources, which reduces their demand for foreign cash. By offering goods and services to a large number of people without needing highly skilled labor, substantial amounts of capital, or sophisticated technology, micro-small businesses have also contributed to the economic transition. Micro-small businesses also readily adapt to the needs of their clients. Additionally, these small companies employ local resources and talents to manufacture a range of goods to meet the requirements of the indigenous people since they are aware of the issues they encounter in Juba City's Konyokonyo Market, Custom Market, and Jebel Market.

Characteristics of Small Businesses in South Sudan

Small enterprises in Juba City that operate at Konyokonyo Market, Custom Market, and Jebel Market have direct access to both local and international financing markets. Small firms operating in Juba City's Konyokonyo Market, Custom Market, and Jebel Market are subject to the same fixed costs for complying with rules as major enterprises, but they have fewer options for exporting their goods. Small companies in Juba City's Konyokonyo Market, Custom Market, and Jebel Market are divided into two groups: organized enterprises, and unstructured businesses.

Organized—They have paid employees with registered offices.

Unorganized: They are made up of South Sudanese who operate outdoors, within temporary wooden shelters, or at home, and they seldom, if ever, hire paid employees. Small businesses in rural areas are typically run by family groups, and the main industries in Konyokonyo Market, Custom Market, and Jebel Market fall under this category. These include soap and detergents, fabrics, clothing and tailoring, textiles and leather, village blacksmiths, tin smiting, bakeries, wood furniture, electronic assembly, ceramics, timber and mining, beverages, food processing, Agro-processing, chemical-based products, and mechanics.

Role of Micro-Small Businesses in South Sudan

In an effort to hasten the role of growth in low income nations, several policy officials have cited small enterprises in the rural and urban regions as one of their top concerns. These tiny firms have been acknowledged as the catalyst for achieving emerging nations' growth goals (Lorretta M, 2014-MSMEs as engine for income and poverty reduction a renewed approach to tackling Urban Poverty in South Sudan). In many developing nations, they are potential sources

of employment and revenue. According to estimates, small companies in emerging nations employ 22% of the adult population (Daniels and Ngwira, 1992; Fisseha, 1992; Daniels and Fisseha, 1993; Fisseha and McPerson, 1991; Gallagler and Robson, 1995).

The important roles performed by Micro-small businesses operating in Konyokonyo Market, Custom Market, Jebel Market in Juba City

Given their highly trained technology, they can react to market situations more readily (Emmanuel K. Okoye, 2008/2009); Repositioning SMEs in Onumba, Anambra State, Nigeria; Micro-small businesses are more adaptable than large corporations, so they have lower capital costs associated with job creation (Anheier and Seibel, 1987; Liedholm and Mead, 1987; Schmitz, 1995); MSME activities, Income levels, and Poverty Reduction; and MSME activities, Employment levels, and Poverty Reduction. Small companies contribute significantly to the development, stability, and employment of the economy; They are more likely to be successful in similar rural and urban areas where they can help to moderate the flow of migration to major cities and contribute to a more equitable distribution of economic activity (Bernard Effah et al., 2014; IJSS-Small and Medium Bamboo and Rattan Enterprises in Economic Empowerment in Kumasi); According to Ogunsiji and Kayode (2010); MSME Contribution of Economic Development), small companies' production units might provide a more equal distribution of income than large firms because of their regional dispersion and labor intensity. Last but not least, micro-small companies boost the effectiveness of the home market and make efficient use of limited resources. Thus, long-term economic growth is made possible. MSMEs are a catalyst for economic growth, entrepreneurship or income production, and poverty alleviation (Beck, Demirguc-Kun, and Marsimovic, 2009).

Policies for Promoting Small Businesses operating in Konyokonyo Market, Custom Market, Jebel Market in Juba City In Juba City's Konyokonyo Market, Custom Market, and Jebel Market, the small and microbusiness sector has been hampered by a lack of political commitment to private sector development, financial institutions' reluctance to take risks, inadequate infrastructure, a lack of entrepreneurial skills, high taxes, bureaucratic red tape, etc. These resulted in increasing inflation and declining real earnings, which drove many workers in the formal sector into side hustles in an effort to make a living wage. Large firm manufacturing employment remained unchanged while the economy deteriorated (Kayanula and Quartey, 2000). Steel and Webster (1991) found that although small businesses and self-employment created 2.9 percent more jobs annually than large businesses did, their operations only contributed a third of the value produced. The government acknowledged the contribution of the informal sector in light of the aforementioned factors. It has acknowledged and given the promotion and expansion of micro-small companies the attention it deserves since they are crucial tools for addressing the problems of unemployment, economic growth, and equity in the nation. They were considered the means of achieving the shift from a state-led economy to a private-oriented developmental model. As a result, the following were added to the newly defined function of the small company sector: (Kayanula and Quartey, 2000) helping the state reduce its direct manufacturing engagement, absorbing workers from the public sector given the relative labor-intensive character of small companies, and fostering indigenous entrepreneurial and management capabilities required for sustained industrialization.

Constraints to micro-small businesses growth and survival

Lack of Capital: It is believed that the biggest issue affecting small and micro business owners is a lack of finance, which appears to be the main cause of company failure. This was backed up by Shafeek (2009), who stated that from a business perspective, without sufficient financing,

the company would be unable to maintain and acquire facilities, recruit and retain qualified staff, produce and market a product, or do any of the other things required to run a successful operation in Konyokonyo Market, Custom Market, and Jebel Market in Juba City. In their book, "Small Business Management and Entrepreneurship," published in 2006, Stokes and Wilson (2006) noted, among other things, that financial problems in Micro and Small Businesses might result from a lack of funding, poor management of the available cash, or a combination of both. They go on to say that new or young small and micro firms with no track record may find it challenging to obtain access to external finances, particularly if the founders lack personal assets to use as collateral. Stokes and Wilson (2006) continue by highlighting the fact that many new owner managers abuse money after receiving them and that small enterprises are renowned for having inadequate financial controls and information. In South Sudan, obtaining financing remained a significant barrier for micro and small companies. Small and micro enterprises typically experience more financial restrictions than do bigger businesses.

Human Resources Management: The key factor in determining whether a small business owner or management will succeed or fail is their competency. A lack of management focus on strategic concerns like human resources management is nearly often the main factor in SME failure or underperformance. Furthermore, since the company is probably going to be indistinguishable from the owner, the early creator of the Micro and Small Business's personal expertise in choosing the correct business and administering it will be vital. When a result, as the firm expands, growth may only be partly quickly if other people are reluctant or unable to assist in managing the agricultural SME (Pasanen, 2006) Additionally, the management of human resources is crucial since it encompasses not just dealing with employee difficulties but also managing external parties that are crucial to the success of the firm, such as essential clients, suppliers, banks, and investors (Stokes and Wilson 2006). In most small and micro company organizations, there is an excessive dependence on the one owner/manager, and this management inclination is one that the owner or manager of the small or micro business is reluctant to change. This results in subpar human resources practices, such as failing to hire new, competent personnel or giving other workers more power and responsibility (Nieman, 2006).

Legal Issue: Micro and small enterprises may be burdened excessively and needlessly by the high start-up expenses for firms in South Sudan, including the licensing and registration procedures. The operations of micro and small firms are negatively impacted by the high expense of resolving legal disputes and lengthy delays in Ministry of Justice and constitutional Development processes. The lengthy process for registering and starting a company is a major problem that is frequently brought up in Juba City, South Sudan's Konyokonyo Market, Custom Market, and Jebel Market. Aryeetey et al. (1994) discovered that less than 1% of their sample was accounted for by this. For the time being, larger companies benefit from the absence of antitrust laws, while access to foreign innovations is restricted for micro-small firms due to a lack of intellectual rights protection.

Information Technology: Technology innovation has always been a major factor in agribusiness development and will continue to have an impact on the expansion and survival of agribusiness SMEs (Baloyi, 2010). Due to their poverty, small and micro agricultural enterprises in developing nations like South Africa lack access to information technology. The inability of small and micro agriculture enterprises to thrive and expand, even in the Alice community area, as a result of this lack of access to information technology (Baloyi, 2010) .

Marketing: Marketing is the sole functional area, according to Shafeek (2009), that connects a company's goods or services with its clients. He continues by saying that it is crucial to make sure that this duty is carried out correctly. A small or micro agricultural enterprise must respond to the fundamental strategic questions, "What markets are we targeting, with what products?" in order to have a decent chance of survival. According to Stokes and Wilson (2006), a weakness in the owners and managers of Micro and Small Businesses is their inability to comprehend critical marketing issues. They hold the opinion that concepts and standards for products and services frequently only reflect the owners' perceptions, which may not be reflected in the market. He continues by saying that modest market changes can bring down freshly founded micro and small businesses, especially if they depend on a select group of clients and operate in Juba City's Konyokonyo Market, Custom Market, and Jebel Market.

Business Plan: A business plan is a written document that meticulously describes the company, its management team, its products/services, and its goals along with methods for achieving those goals, according to Nieman and Nieuwenhuizen (2009). It is a live document that is included in the formal planning processes that businesses use, and it acts as a tool for lowering the chance that a venture would fail, a benchmark for a firm's internal performance, as well as a vehicle for obtaining funding (Nieman and Nieuwenhuizen, 2009). Small and micro businesses do not have appropriate business plans since they do not typically engage in formal planning. As a result, they are unable to evaluate the company's internal performance, are unable to get funding such as loans, and are exposed to a larger risk of business collapse. A business plan should be revised frequently since it is a dynamic document that will improve the chances of success for SMEs at Konyokonyo Market, Custom Market, and Jebel Market in Juba City.

Methodology

We talk about the techniques used to conduct out data collecting under methodology. It outlines the demographic and sample that were chosen, the process used to choose the sample, how the instrument was developed and designed, how the questionnaire and interviews were administered, and the process used to analyze the results.

Research Design

The descriptive research survey was the study design used. The study's goal to define a population's characteristic by choosing a sample of micro-small company owners who would fill out questionnaires made the design chosen for the study adequate. The design was also picked because it was seen to be the most suitable, pertinent, and would deliver the required data at the lowest cost and in the shortest amount of time. Additionally, the design would guarantee a better level of precision and dependability.

Methods of Data Collection

The necessary data for this study was gathered using a variety of related but distinct procedures in order to acquire extremely accurate information. Primary and secondary sources make up the two main data sources.

Primary Data

The primary method of data collection takes into consideration the following instruments:

Questionnaire: This method involves approaching respondents with a series of written or spoken inquiries that will allow for a range of opinions and responses. Before being widely circulated, the questionnaires created for this study were carefully created, pre-tested with a

sample of responders, and fixed. This was done with the intention of identifying and eliminating respondents who were unable to reply to certain questions.

Interviews: Here, in order to get the required data, the researcher speaks with the respondents directly. Interviews will be done regarding issues that weren't covered by the disseminated questionnaire. The researcher was also able to explain certain unclear questions thanks to the in-person interviews.

Secondary Data: Documentary sources constituted the majority of the secondary data sources. These include data that was gathered via the internet, numerous libraries that were visited, and government documents.

Target audience

The target group included 60 owners of micro-small companies in Juba's Konyokonyo Market, including those in the construction, carpentry, farming, hairdressing, auto repairs, art and craft, financial services, and agricultural industries.

Sample Procedure

The snowball sampling technique was employed to choose respondents from small firms for the study.

Sample Size

51 microbusiness owners from various businesses in the Konyokonyo Market, Custom Market, and Jebel Market in Juba City made up the sample size for the study.

Research Instrument

Face-to-face interviews and questionnaires were the methods used to collect enough data.

Administration of the Instruments

The copies of the questionnaires were individually distributed to the respondents by the researcher. The owner-managers of the numerous micro-small enterprises were asked for their permission. Five full days were allocated to the micro-small company owners to complete the questionnaire and interviews.

Method of Data Analysis Simple tables were used in this study's data analysis, which required processing the questionnaire's data to provide a relevant interpretation. The distribution of the answers provided by respondents to each questionnaire question was clearly displayed using the tables.

Findings and Data Analysis

The information gathered and processed in Chapter 4 is presented and explained in this chapter. As a case study, the data analysis in Chapter 4 focused on the challenges encountered by micro and small businesses in the Konyokonyo Market, Custom Market, and Jebel Market in the capital city of Juba. A total of fifty-one (51) questionnaires were sent out to the respondents for the research; all of them received complete responses and were returned. The study deemed the surveys to be informative and pertinent, and they made up the entirety of the questionnaires distributed to respondents. The following came to light after careful reading and sophisticated statistical analysis of our data. It is presented to the reader as a frequency table for comprehension. The panelists agreed that South Sudan's micro, small, and medium-sized businesses are extremely important to the country's development and economic

progress. Some of the contributions made by the sector, as described during the data collection in the field, are listed below and shown in the table.

Table 1: contribution of small and medium-sized businesses

Contribution of Small and Medium Enterprises	Frequency	Percent
Small micro Business contribute to Gross Domestic Product	5	9.8
Small micro Business contribute to Employment in Juba Markets	6	11.8
Small micro Business contribute to Poverty Reduction in Juba Markets	7	13.7
Small micro Business contribute to Income Generation in South Sudan	4	7.8
Small Micro Business contribute to Growth & Development	6	11.8
Small Micro Business contribute to Industrial Dynamics	7	13.7
Small Micro Business contribute to Services Provision	3	5.9
Small Micro Business contribute to Growth & Specialization	2	3.9
Small Micro Business contribute to Competitive Advantage	6	11.8
Small Micro Business contribute to Food Production & Consumption	5	9.8
Total	51	100.0

Source: Authors computation 2022

Table 2. Table Results below of the constraints facing micro small Business growth

Variable	Frequency	Percent %
Lack of business training	3	5.88

Capital constraints	4	7.84
Lack of access to finance	5	9.80
Poor infrastructure	4	7.84
Poor production	3	5.88
Poor technologies	4	7.84
Tight regulations	4	7.84
Corruption	3	5.88
Poor market accessibility	4	7.84
Motivation of business owners	9	17.65
Limited access to information	2	3.92
Lack of human competencies	2	3.92
Inadequate raw materials	4	7.84
Total	51	100.00

Source: Authors computation 2022

Table 3: Most Severe Constraints faced by Micro, Small, Medium in konyokonyo market

Constraint	Frequency	Percent %
Marketing and competition	10	19.61
Insufficient capital	6	11.76
Lack of credit	4	7.84
Poor infrastructure	16	31.37
Insecurity	7	13.73
Lack of required skills	8	15.69
Total	51	100.00

Source: Authors computation 2022

Table above highlights the major constraints faced by Micro Business in the Konyokonyo market with marketing and competition together with lack of sufficient capital and credit being the major constraints.

Table.4: Comparative analysis of Micro, Small, Medium in East Africa Community Countries

Category of Business	Kenya	Uganda	South Sudan	Rwanda	Burundi	Tanzania
Number of Employees						
Micro	1-10	1-4	-	1-3	-	0-5
Small	11-50	5-50	-	3-30	-	5-49
Medium	51-100	50-100	-	30-100	-	50-99
Capital Investments						
	Kenya K Shs		Uganda U Shs	South Sudan SSP	Rwanda Frw	Burundi
Micro	-	-	0-10m	0-0.5m	-	0-5m
Small	-	-	10-100m	0.5-15m	-	5-200m
Medium	-	-	100-360m	15-75m	-	200-800m

Source: Authors computation 2022

Discussion of the findings

The results showed that the sector cannot be disregarded due to the importance of micro, small, and medium-sized businesses to the national economies of sub-Saharan Africa. As this article has shown, micro, small, and medium-sized businesses contributed more than 13.2 percent of South Sudan's gross domestic product and supported an employment rate of 62.0 percent on average. However, it is a reality that most governments give little attention to small and medium-sized businesses and have not put in place the necessary infrastructure to support the sector's growth. Despite the contributions made by South Sudan's micro, small, and medium-sized businesses, the sector faces a number of obstacles that, if resolved by the government, would allow it to continue to lead the country in innovation and development. These obstacles include a lack of power and electricity, financial accessibility, management of skills and competencies, information dissemination, government support, training and capacity building, and corruption. Through the beneficial role and contributions of the Micro, Small & Medium Business, South Sudan was able to establish itself as a competitive behemoth and shift its economic standing to other parts of the world. East Africa, and South Sudan in particular, have abundant oil, agricultural products, fisheries, livestock, minerals, water resources, and people resources that can handle the majority of problems brought on by the Americas, Asia, and Europe. Finally, this paper identified a potential strategy for assisting small and medium-sized businesses in South Sudan by improving their ability to communicate effectively, raising knowledge of the industry, and obtaining support from national and international donors.

SUMMARY

According to the findings, micro, small, and medium-sized businesses have made significant contributions to the growth of African economies. Contributions from small and medium-sized businesses include: Micro, Small & medium Business contributes to GDP, Micro, Small & medium Business contribute to Employment, Micro, Small & medium Business contribute to

poverty reduction, Micro, Small & medium Business contribute to income generation, Micro, Small & medium Business contribute to South Sudan economic Growth & development, Micro, Small & medium Business contribute to Industrial Dynamics, Micro, Small & medium Business contribute to Services Provision, Micro, Small & medium Business contribute to Growth & Specialization, Micro, Small & medium Business contribute to competitive advantage, Micro, Small & medium Business contribute to Food Production & Consumption. While the goal of starting a micro, small, and medium business is to provide employment for the unemployed, aid in reducing poverty levels in South Sudan, empower women, provide for their families, advance the African economy, produce goods and services for foreign markets, supply resources and materials to large businesses, improve standards of living, and engage in economic activity. Despite the above contributions made by micro, small, and medium-sized businesses, which were mentioned by respondents in South Sudan, the sector still faces a number of difficulties, including: an electricity problem; a lack of funding; poor management; low levels of education; inadequate training and capacity building; a lack of access to reliable information; incompetence; a lack of government support; poor record-keeping and subpar reporting standards; and corruption. These issues provide very serious barriers to the expansion of South Sudan's micro, small, and medium-sized businesses. The parties involved, notably the South Sudanese government, should contribute with the right solutions to these concerns, particularly the ones involving power and money. In South Sudan, there are also chances for micro, small, and medium-sized businesses. These opportunities include: big markets are available for them from major corporations; government involvement in them; and entrepreneurs' interest in them. Politicians' interest in micro, small, and medium-sized businesses More economic growth, potential customers for SMEs' resources and materials, potential customers for their goods and services, increased demand from international markets, potential for more SMEs to operate in the future, and other possibilities.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the goal of this essay is to investigate how tiny businesses, or "microbusinesses," might contribute to economic progress. Konyokonyo Market, Custom Market, and Jebel Market in Juba, South Sudan, were the case studies used. The reason for the development of micro, small, and medium businesses, as well as their obstacles and answers for small, medium, and micro businesses and the possibilities for the nations of East Africa. Through GDP, job creation, and rising income levels, small and medium-sized businesses significantly contribute to the South Sudanese economy. Both the gross domestic product and the GDP show that the gross domestic product per capita has a strong and significant positive connection. However, the importance of small, medium-sized businesses to the broader economy increases with a country's wealth. Once more, the findings showed extremely strong evidence of the impact of micro, small, and medium-sized businesses to socioeconomic situations and the decrease of poverty. These businesses also offer a variety of services and chances for employment. Consequently, this research of micro, small, and medium-sized businesses discovered a beneficial influence on GDP per capita, employment, and poverty reduction in the South Sudan. Additionally, the results demonstrate that while traditional banks refuse to extend credit to micro, small, and medium-sized businesses due to collateral issues, microfinance institutions support SMEs by organizing training programs for them, providing them with credit, and providing advice on how to use credit wisely, manage risk, and develop a culture of saving and investing. The survey also finds that the lack of funding and electrical problems are the two biggest obstacles facing micro, small, and medium-sized businesses in Juba City's Konyokonyo Market, Custom Market, and Jebel Market. Poor management and insufficient government and donor assistance are additional difficulties faced by micro, small, and medium-sized businesses.

Recommendations

The government of South Sudan is advised by this research study to assist in creating significant and beneficial policies that are supportive of the growth of micro, small, and medium-sized businesses. In order to develop effective strategies for their successes and sustainability in the numerous marketplaces functioning in Konyokonyo Market, Custom Market, and Jebel Market in Juba City, South Sudan, Micro, Small & Medium Businesses (MSMB) should be placed on the government's agenda. Additionally, for the sector to continue creating jobs by assisting in the reduction of poverty and the provision of income to the communities, adequate regulatory framework, good infrastructure, continuous electricity supply, and financial support for micro, Small & Medium Businesses. in Konyokonyo Market, Custom Market, and Jebel Market in Juba City should be available. The study also urges the government to seriously consider financing micro, small, and medium-sized businesses through significant budgetary allotment and donations to these businesses in order to improve the conditions and living standards of the underprivileged and ultimately to contribute to the economic growth, prosperity, and sustainability of the sector in the nation. The South Sudanese government should also urge donor partners and organizations to support small and medium-sized businesses in Juba City's Konyokonyo Market, Custom Market, and Jebel Market. To reduce default risk from micro, small, and medium-sized business operators, they should create rules, guidelines, and regulations.

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